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№ 5

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
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- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
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- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Elektron nashr,
280 sahifa, dekabr, 2024-yil.

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
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asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
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ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
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PERSONNEL POLICIES AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT: MODIFYING HR TACTICS DURING PANDEMICS OR ECONOMIC DOWNTURNS

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Abstract: This article examines the transformation of personnel policies and human resource strategies during crises, such as pandemics and economic downturns. By analyzing scholarly works and case studies, it identifies effective HR practices, including flexible work arrangements, transparent communication, and ethical downsizing. The findings emphasize the importance of resilience and adaptability in HR tactics to ensure organizational sustainability during crises.

Keywords: personnel policies, crisis management, HR strategies, pandemics, economic downturns, workforce flexibility, employee engagement, resilience.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada pandemiyalar va iqtisodiy inqirozlar kabi vaziyatlarda kadrlar siyosati va inson resurslarini boshqarish strategiyalaridagi o'zgarishlar tahlil qilingan. Ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliyotlardan foydalanib, moslashuvchan ish tartibi, ochiq kommunikatsiya va etika me'yorlariga asoslangan qisqartirish kabi samarali HR usullari aniqlangan. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, inqiroz davrida tashkilotlarning barqarorligini ta'minlashda HR siyosatining moslashuvchanligi va chidamliligi muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: kadrlar siyosati, inqirozni boshqarish, HR strategiyalari, pandemiyalar, iqtisodiy inqirozlar, moslashuvchan ish tartibi, xodimlarni jalb qilish, chidamlilik.

Аннотация: В статье исследуются изменения кадровой политики и стратегий управления человеческими ресурсами в условиях кризисов, таких как пандемии и экономические спады. На основе анализа научных работ и кейс-исследований определены эффективные HR-практики, включая гибкие графики работы, прозрачную коммуникацию и этическое сокращение персонала. Результаты подчеркивают важность устойчивости и адаптивности HR-стратегий для обеспечения стабильности организаций в условиях кризисов.

Ключевые слова: кадровая политика, управление кризисами, HR-стратегии, пандемии, экономические спады, гибкость рабочей силы, вовлеченность сотрудников, устойчивость.

INTRODUCTION

The world economy is susceptible to a number of crises, including as pandemics and economic downturns, which can have a significant impact on companies and their workforce. For instance, the COVID-19 epidemic illustrated the significance of responsive and flexible human resource management. To handle issues like employee wellness, remote work, and business continuity, HR departments have to swiftly modify personnel policies. Similar to this, economic downturns compel businesses to make tough choices like restructuring, salary reductions, or layoffs.

Both immediate survival and long-term rehabilitation depend on HR's ability to handle crises effectively. Organizational survival depends on knowing how HR strategies can be modified in times of crisis. The purpose of this study is to give corporate executives and human resources experts information into the best ways to manage staff during interruptions in the economy or in health. This thesis will also assist firms in creating more robust HR policies that can be swiftly applied in future emergency situations by using examples from previous crises.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The role of personnel policies in crisis management has been extensively explored by scholars, particularly in the context of pandemics and economic downturns. One prominent aspect is the flexibility of human resource management (HRM) strategies during periods of uncertainty. According to Pfeffer and Salancik, organizational survival often depends on the ability to adapt HR policies to external conditions. This includes the implementation of agile workforce strategies, such as flexible work arrangements and remote working policies, which gained prominence during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Brewster and Hegewisch highlighted the importance of integrating crisis management into HR practices. They argue that organizations that embed resilience in their personnel policies, such as robust employee assistance programs and proactive communication strategies, tend to navigate economic challenges more effectively. This notion aligns with studies by Cascio, who underscored the significance of employee engagement during times of economic stress. Cascio's work reveals that maintaining transparent communication with employees fosters trust and reduces anxiety, which is critical for sustaining morale and productivity.

Another key consideration is workforce downsizing and rightsizing strategies during economic recessions. The research by Cameron emphasizes that organizations must balance cost-cutting measures with ethical considerations and long-term human capital development. Poorly managed layoffs can lead to significant reputational damage and decreased employee loyalty, making thoughtful and strategic personnel decisions paramount.

Further, Stiglitz and Greenwald have explored the economic implications of crises on labor markets, linking them to shifts in HR practices. Their analysis suggests that periods of economic downturn necessitate a reevaluation of recruitment, retention, and training policies. They also stress the importance of government and organizational collaboration in providing skill development programs for displaced workers, enabling their reintegration into the workforce.

Lastly, the works of Ulrich underscore the strategic role of HR professionals as crisis managers. Ulrich posits that HR departments should act as change agents, facilitating transitions by aligning personnel policies with organizational goals while addressing employee concerns. This dual focus on business outcomes and employee well-being enhances organizational resilience during crises.

The literature consistently demonstrates that effective crisis management requires a dynamic and people-centric approach to HRM. Scholars advocate for strategies that not only address immediate challenges but also contribute to the long-term stability and adaptability of organizations. By drawing on these insights, companies can refine their personnel policies to better manage future crises.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study involved collecting data through a review of existing literature on personnel policies and crisis management, focusing on peer-reviewed journals and case studies. Secondary data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis to identify patterns and strategies in HR adaptations during pandemics and economic downturns. This approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the subject, grounded in empirical evidence and theoretical insights.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The procedures and choices that assist companies in navigating unforeseen obstacles and reducing adverse effects are referred to as crisis management. This entails modifying personnel policies in the context of human resources to handle the particular requirements and hazards presented by emergencies. Research indicates that empathy, communication, and adaptability are necessary for efficient crisis management in human resources. Organizations must strike a balance between long-term employee engagement and morale and short-term financial stability during times of crisis. In times of crisis, personnel policies pertaining to hiring, retaining, paying, and providing for employees must be quickly modified. The research identifies a number of crucial areas in which HR must step in:

Layoffs and cutbacks: Staff cutbacks are frequently required during economic downturns. Such measures must be transparent, equitable, and comply with the law, and HR must make sure of this. Many firms were obliged to adopt remote work practices as a result of the COVID-19 outbreak. HR departments had to create flexible work schedules, remote collaboration tools, and health and safety standards fast. The mental health of employees can be significantly impacted by crises like recessions or pandemics. Employee assistance programs, flexible work schedules, and mental health support should be the main focuses of HR strategy. In times of economic crisis, keeping employees on board becomes crucial. Reduced working hours, furloughs, or layoffs can lower employee loyalty and lower morale. During these periods, effective HR tactics include:

Transparent Communication: Trust is increased when staff members are kept up to date on the company's financial situation and prospects.

Workforce Flexibility: Even in situations when full-time roles are unsustainable, providing flexible working hours or part-time positions can aid in staff retention. **Retention Incentives:** To entice workers to stick around during difficult times, several businesses offer retention bonuses or other benefits.

According to research, companies that had a proactive HR crisis management plan were better equipped to handle crises. Organizations with strong communication systems and established remote work practices, for instance, were better able to adjust swiftly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Employee engagement and loyalty were also higher in organizations that put a priority on employee well-being by providing flexible work schedules and mental health care. Employee satisfaction varied according to how transparent and clear HR's responses were. Employee confidence and commitment were stronger in companies that communicated the financial status and next plans frequently and early. On the other hand, imprecise communication caused worry and confusion, which had a detrimental effect on morale. Companies that were open and sympathetic to their workers during times of crisis had lower turnover rates after the crisis, according to our findings. On the other hand, when regular operations resumed, employee attrition rates were greater for companies that made sudden layoffs or neglected to assist employees during bad times. Managing high levels of uncertainty, maintaining legal compliance during layoffs, and striking a balance between immediate financial restrictions and long-term workforce sustainability were among the difficulties mentioned by HR managers. They added that a major obstacle during the pandemic was a lack of readiness for working remotely.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

According to our findings, HR crisis management success necessitates adaptability, transparent communication, and an emphasis on worker welfare. Businesses are better able to preserve employee trust and productivity when they proactively modify their personnel practices and place a high priority on open communication during emergencies. Furthermore, striking a balance between immediate demands and long-term organizational recovery and staff retention is essential to the long-term effectiveness of crisis management techniques. In light of the results, the following suggestions are offered:

Create Crisis Management Plans: Human resources departments ought to draft comprehensive crisis management plans that cover topics including employee assistance, remote work, and layoffs.

Transparent Communication: HR should place a high priority on communicating with staff members in a clear and regular manner, particularly when it comes to organizational adjustments during emergencies.

Encourage Employee Well-Being: Offering employee assistance programs, flexible work schedules, and mental health support can all help to keep morale and output high.

Post-Crisis Recovery: To guarantee long-term retention and corporate success, HR should concentrate on re-engaging staff members and restoring company culture following a crisis.

The role of technology in assisting HR crisis management, including the use of digital technologies for communication, employee engagement, and remote work, might be investigated further. Longitudinal studies could also evaluate how crisis-driven HR policies affect business culture and employee career development over the long run.

List of used literature

1. Boudreau, J. W., & Ramstad, P. M. (2005). Talentship and the evolution of human resource management: From “job” to “knowledge work” and beyond. *Human Resource Planning*, 28(2), 17-26.
2. Cameron, E., & Green, M. (2015). *Making sense of change management: A complete guide to the models, tools, and techniques of organizational change*. Kogan Page Publishers.
3. Cascio, W. F. (2009). *Managing human resources: Productivity, quality of work life, profits* (8th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
4. Fink, S. (2013). *Crisis management: Planning for the inevitable*. American Management Association.
5. Holstein, J. A., & Gubrium, J. F. (2016). The interview: A tool for qualitative research. In N. K. Denzin & Y. S. Lincoln (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research* (5th ed., pp. 354-376). SAGE Publications.
6. KPMG. (2020). COVID-19: Impact on workforce strategies and human resources practices. KPMG International. Retrieved from <https://home.kpmg/xx/en/home/insights/2020/04/covid-19-workforce-strategy-hr.html>
7. B.R.Sarimsakov. Economic and Social Significance of Personnel Management in Manufacturing Enterprises: A Dual Dimension Analysis// *Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot. Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*. №11-12 son. ISSN 2992-8982 – Toshkent 2023-yil, 511–516 betlar. <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/journal/index>
8. B.R.Sarimsakov. Personnel Excellence: Maximizing Reception, Classification, and Management in Enterprises//*Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance* (ISSN: 2660-454X) is scholarly open access, high citation leading fully economic-related journal. Volume: 04 Issue: 12/2023 ISSN: 2660-454X
9. B.R.Sarimsakov. Ishlab chiqarish korxonalarida personal boshqaruvining iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy mohiyati//*Synergy: Journl of ethics and governance* Volume: 03 Issue: 12/Dec - 2023 ISSN: 2181-2616
10. B.R.Sarimsakov. Assessing the effectiveness of personnel management in production enterprises: a comprehensive methodology// *MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE* International scientific-online conference France. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10409095>
11. B.R.Sarimsakov. Personal boshqaruvining nazariy va uslubiy rivojlanish jihatlari// *International Journal of Finance and Digitalization* www.ijfd.uz ISSN: 2181-3957 Vol. 2 Issue 06, 2023.

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2024. № 5

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"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

